

Positioning, Performance, Problems and Prospects of Digital Marketing firms in India

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Abstract

Digital marketing has become a genre of business. With progressively number of organizations picking to make a brand picture on the web and connect with the crowd universally, the technicalities around the web are likewise expanding. Websites, sites, marketing efforts, SEO procedures, and so on have entered profound into the measurements of the technicality that impacts one's essence on the web. Digital marketing is a big umbrella under which the technical, just as non-technical skills to make an influx of prevalence over the web, is secured. The business has made an assortment of jobs for people to look for work and show their gifts. It takes experts from the field of web designing, web improvement, online life consultants, brand consultants, content writers, visual fashioner, specialists, and so forth to meet up and on the whole work towards making a visual portrayal of thoughts that is anything but difficult to plant into the psyches of the crowd. As the business develops, the interest for inventive experts in the field is rising also creating greater work in India and making India a center point for IT exercises. This article reviews four conceptual and contextual dimensions of digital marketing firms in India.

Keywords: Digital Marketing, Digital marketing firms Positioning, Performance, Problems and Prospects.

Introduction

Internet access is a main-stream thing. It has heightened the utilization of PCs, mobile telephones, and PCs prompting a high change in the growth of digital stations both in volume and quality. Be it surfing for data on Google, web based life, or making buys, India has changed this medium into an undeniable big market. What's more, this market has prospered into making Digital Marketing as a significant wellspring of bringing business through the internet! Digital Marketing is developing at a sensational pace of 25-30% in India yearly. Furthermore, if statistics are to be accepted, India has arrived at a challenging number of 500 million users of the internet before the finish of 2018. India likewise brags of the World's biggest Facebook populace. The rapid digitization, web based life channels, online entryways, and so forth has prompted a growth of digital marketing in a pattern standard creative mind.

Word-by-mouth exposure, entryway to entryway promotion, radio declarations, TV commercials – Indian firms have consistently depended on customary strategies for marketing. Until the internet occurred! The devices of marketing changed from people to devices. It got simpler to infiltrate through an enormous fragment of the audience with negligible endeavors. Also, as the quantity of PC and mobile telephone users continues extending, digital marketing could spread its wings wide and far.

The earliest instances of online availability were represented with the presentation of Michael Aldrich online shopping framework. In the next years, the Thomson Holidays UK was propelled, at that point came the India MART B2B in 1996. In any case, it was eventually in 2007 that the dispatch of Flipkart, a web based business marketing website drastically changed the structure of marketing in India. What followed was an ascent in the quantity of individuals getting mobile telephones, at-home conveyance, online shopping, and internet marketing as a way to promote the brands. What's more, throughout the years the Digital Marketing Industry in India has thrived into bringing an enormous percent of business online with its promising capacity to make a worldwide system and prosper even the independent ventures universally. As indicated by the International Journal of Advanced Research Foundation, India is going through a brilliant time of digital marketing growth since the time 2013 and the pattern proceeds till at any rate 2020.

On a normal an Indian goes through around 4-5 hours daily looking through messages, online networking, and programs. The developing business sector of devices like cell phones, tablets, PCs, and so forth has immensely expanded the pace of use and infiltrated the market to make it reach to a more extensive arrangement of audience. The content on the internet impacts the lives of individuals big time. Show of thoughts through pictures, recordings, messages, and so on leaves a sound establishment into the psyches of the individuals which converts into their living. Digital marketing is generally about affecting the audience online with mechanisms of content to build a brand's effect over the audience. The measure of time spent by the individuals on the internet empowers digital advertisers to make effective techniques to impact consumer behavior. The correct strategy changes over the audience into sales.

From just around 70 million online customers in 2016 and in excess of 100 million of every 2017, India has seen a sharp ascent in the internet populace. Since the time the dispatch of Digital India in 2015 as an activity to improve online infrastructure and digital strengthening, there has been mushrooming of a total market of new businesses, administrations and more than interface individuals all inclusive! It has brought about an ascent of dynamic internet users, mobile connections, online networking traffic and the sky is the limit from there.

Digital marketing has become a genre of business. With more number of businesses picking to create a brand image online and reach out to the audience all around, the technicalities around the internet are additionally increasing. Websites, online journals, marketing efforts, SEO strategies, etc. have penetrated deep into the metrics of the technicality that influences one's presence on the internet. As a result, it takes some well-equipped experts to create a social representing a brand. Over the previous decade, the digital marketing agencies and professionals with deep knowledge into the field have emerged to cater to the needs. With sound skills, imaginative personalities and second to none knowledge of what will work for a business online – these experts are the banner bearers of digital marketing.

Digital marketing is a big umbrella under which the technical, just as non-technical skills to create a wave of notoriety over the internet, is covered. The business has created a variety of job roles for people to seek employment and show their talents. It takes experts from the field of web designing, web development, online life consultants, brand consultants, content writers, visual designer, specialists, etc. to come together and collectively progress in the direction of creating a visual representation of ideas that is easy to plant into the psyches of the audience. As the business develops, the demand for creative experts in the field is rising also generating more employment in India and making India a center point for IT activities.

The return on investment for businesses through digital stages has exceeded than that from real life stages. Companies are today moving towards a more digitally empowered set-up to make the greater part of the golden period of digital marketing that India is witnessing. Around 70-80% of the population is dedicated to making purchases online, and e-commerce websites like Flipkart, Amazon, Myntra, etc are causing a ripple effect with their influence over the market. As the access to the internet over a larger population rises, India is to witness a revolution in terms of digitalization that will before long make India as one of the top markets on the planet with the highest numbers of internet users. Online webcasts, web stories, entertainment, sports, business, social awareness and career in India gets more dependent on digital stages for generating revenue, sharing data and nation's progress, Digital Marketing is becoming a promising industry with fast career growth, increasing influences, and widespread activities!

This study takes a 4-dimensional view of Digital Marketing firms in India. These four dimensions are - Positioning, Performance, Problems and Prospects.

The following table explains these four dimensions –

Table 1: 4-dimensions of the study explained

Sr. No.	Dimension	Domain of study
1	Positioning	How has digital marketing positioned itself in India vis-à-vis traditional marketing? Is the positioning strategic or tactical?
2	Performance	What has been the growth of digital marketing over the last 10 years?
3	Problems	What are the pain areas for digital marketing?
4	Prospects	What are the prospects for digital marketing in India?

The areas under the domain of digital marketing are given below and these would be studied in the framework of the 4 dimensions stated above –

1. Affiliate Marketing
2. Content Creation
3. Digital Display Advertising
4. Digital Media Planning and Buying
5. Email Marketing
6. Interactive Marketing
7. Mobile Marketing
8. Online Public Relations (Online PR)
9. Search Engine Marketing (SEM)
10. Search Engine Optimization (SEO)
11. Social Media Marketing (SMM)
12. Viral Marketing
13. Web Analytics

Review of Literature

A number of research papers and articles provide a detailed insight on Digital Marketing. The findings from the literature are presented below:-

Internet marketing has been described essentially as 'achieving marketing objectives through applying digital technologies' (Chaffey et al., 2009). Digital marketing is the use of technologies to help marketing activities so as to improve customer knowledge by coordinating their needs (Chaffey, 2013). In the developed world, companies have realized the importance of digital marketing. With the goal for businesses to be successful they should merge online with customary methods for meeting the needs of customers more precisely (Shankar et. al, 2011). Presentation of new technologies has creating new business opportunities for marketers to manage their websites and achieve their business objectives (Kiani, 1998). Online advertising is a powerful marketing vehicle for building brands and increasing traffic for companies to achieve success (Song, 2001). Expectations in terms of creating results and measuring success for advertisement money spent, digital marketing is more cost-efficient for measuring ROI on advertisement (Pepelnjak, 2008).

Today, tedious advertising and marketing techniques have given approach to digital marketing. What's more, it is ground-breaking to such an extent that it can help revive the economy and can create tremendous opportunities for governments to work in a more efficient manner (Munshi, 2012). Firms in Singapore have tested the success of digital marketing apparatuses as being effective and useful for achieving results. (Teo, 2005). More significantly, growth in digital marketing has been due to the fast advances in technologies and changing market elements (Mort, Sullivan, Drennan, Judy, 2002).

All together for digital marketing to deliver result for businesses, digital content, for example, accessibility, route and speed are defined as the key characteristics for marketing (Kanttila, 2004). Other tried and tested instrument for achieving success through digital marketing is the use of informal WOM via web-based networking media and for making the site well known (Trusov, 2009). Likewise, WOM is linked with creating new members and increasing traffic on the website which in return increases the perceivability in terms of marketing.

Web based life with an extra normal example Facebook has opened the entryway for businesses to communicate with a huge number of people about items and services and has opened new marketing opportunities in the market. This is possible just if the managers are completely aware of utilizing the correspondence strategies to engage the customers and enhancing their experience (Mangold, 2009). Marketing professional should genuinely understand online social marketing efforts and programs and understand how to do it effectively with performance measurement pointers. As the market elements everywhere throughout the world are changing in relation to the youthful audience accessibility to online networking and usage. It is significant that strategic integration approaches are adopted in association's marketing correspondence plan (Rohm and Hanna, 2011).

Online journals as an apparatus for digital marketing have successfully created an effect for increasing sales revenue, especially for items where customers can read reviews and write comments about personal experiences. For businesses, online reviews have worked really well as a major aspect of their overall strategic marketing strategy (Zhang, 2013). Online services apparatuses are more influencing than conventional methods of correspondence (Helm, Moller, Mauroner, Conrad, 2013). As a feature of study, it is proven that users experience increase in self-esteem and enjoyment when they adjust to online networking which itself is a persuading sign for businesses and marketing professional (Arnott, 2013). Web experiences affect the mental process of consumers and enhance their purchasing decision online (Cetină, Cristiana, Rădulescu, 2012).

The Internet is the most powerful instrument for businesses (Yannopoulos, 2011). Marketing managers who neglect to utilize the importance of the Internet in their business marketing strategy will be at disadvantage because the Internet is changing the brand, evaluating, dissemination and advancement strategy.

Research Gap

Most of the studies have been done on one or two dimensions of digital marketing. A comprehensive study involving something like four variables is not seen on record. Hence this 4-dimensional study of digital marketing in India is proposed to be undertaken to provide a holistic view of the concept.

Methodology

Following methodology was designed for the study to collect primary data.

- a. Identify a database of the digital marketing firms in India
- b. Conduct a survey seeking ranking of the four dimensions - Positioning, Performance, Problems and Prospects for the 13 areas of digital marketing
- c. Summarize the responses
- d. Analyze the results

www.soravjain.com (2015) provides a list of 710 digital marketing agencies and social media companies located all over India. A short-survey was sent to 685 agencies whose e-mail addresses were available. The survey was closed on the receipt of the 400th response.

The survey had 4 sections with 5 factors each with response scheme as under –

Table 2: Response ratings for the four dimensions

Sr. No.	Dimension	Rating options
1	Positioning	Very well positioned, Well positioned, Neutral, Poorly positioned, Very poorly positioned
2	Performance	Excellent performance, Good performance, Neutral, Poor performance, Disgusting performance
3	Problems	Very strong problem, Strong problem, Neutral, Not much of a problem, Not a problem at all
4	Prospects	Very strong prospect, Strong prospect, Neutral, Not much of a prospect, Not a prospect at all

Responses were analyzed on the basis of simple classification and tabulation.

Results and discussion

Results

a. Descriptive analysis of the sample (Table set 3)

Location of respondents

Sr. No.	Area	Number of agency respondents	Percentage
1	Mumbai	60	15%
2	Pune	48	12%
3	Chennai	44	11%
4	Delhi	40	10%
5	Hyderabad	40	10%
6	Bhopal	40	10%
7	Nagpur	40	10%
8	Kolkatta	32	8%
9	Bengaluru	32	8%
10	Others	24	6%
	Total	400	100%

Experience in digital marketing

Sr. No.	Experience	Number of agency respondents	Percentage
1	< 5 years	202	51%
2	5-10 years	165	41%
3	>10 years	33	8%
	Total	400	100%

Number of services offered

Sr. No.	Number of services offered	Number of agency respondents	Percentage
1	< 5	102	26%
2	5-10	184	46%
3	>10	114	29%
	Total	400	100%

Number of employees

Sr. No.	Number of employees	Number of agency respondents	Percentage
1	<10	185	46%
2	10-25	115	29%
3	>25	100	25%
	Total	400	100%

Analysis of four dimensions

Responses to Positioning

Table 4: Responses to Positioning

Sr. No.	Area	Very well positioned	Well positioned	Neutral	Poorly positioned	Very poorly positioned	Total
1	Search Engine Optimization (SEO)	112	145	25	64	54	400
2	Search Engine Marketing (SEM)	155	158	30	13	44	400
3	Content Creation	105	136	19	83	57	400
4	Social Media Marketing (SMM)	68	56	17	190	69	400
5	Digital Display Advertising	59	150	25	66	100	400
6	Mobile Marketing	57	156	35	80	72	400
7	Interactive Marketing	121	186	23	49	21	400
8	Viral Marketing	47	198	36	28	91	400
9	Email Marketing	210	116	26	18	30	400
10	Affiliate Marketing	138	146	29	58	29	400
11	Online Public Relations (Online PR)	130	126	17	48	79	400
12	Digital Media Planning and Buying	106	152	41	56	45	400
13	Web Analytics	136	114	26	97	27	400
	Total	1444	1839	349	850	718	5200
	Percentage	28%	35%	7%	16%	14%	100%

Responses to Performance

Table 5: Responses to Performance

Sr. No.	Area	Excellent	Good	Neutral	Poor	Disgusting	Total
1	Search Engine Optimization (SEO)	139	127	29	60	45	400
2	Search Engine Marketing (SEM)	81	185	24	69	41	400
3	Content Creation	94	212	20	25	49	400
4	Social Media Marketing (SMM)	75	180	41	48	56	400
5	Digital Display Advertising	80	169	43	75	33	400
6	Mobile Marketing	63	226	37	26	48	400
7	Interactive Marketing	98	155	28	68	51	400
8	Viral Marketing	140	120	30	63	47	400
9	Email Marketing	100	160	31	59	50	400
10	Affiliate Marketing	101	202	43	27	27	400
11	Online Public Relations (Online PR)	88	208	34	41	29	400
12	Digital Media Planning and Buying	128	151	22	65	34	400
13	Web Analytics	113	163	38	54	32	400
	Total	1300	2258	420	680	542	5200
	Percentage	25%	43%	8%	13%	10%	100%

Responses to Problems

Table 6: Responses to Problems

Sr. No.	Area	Very strong	Strong	Neutral	Not much	Not at all	Total
1	Search Engine Optimization (SEO)	64	192	30	72	42	400
2	Search Engine Marketing (SEM)	64	190	44	54	48	400
3	Content Creation	74	222	32	35	37	400
4	Social Media Marketing (SMM)	51	215	43	35	56	400
5	Digital Display Advertising	130	124	39	48	59	400
6	Mobile Marketing	125	154	28	53	40	400
7	Interactive Marketing	102	171	38	36	53	400
8	Viral Marketing	141	163	22	34	40	400
9	Email Marketing	96	185	40	42	37	400
10	Affiliate Marketing	83	195	23	47	52	400
11	Online Public Relations (Online PR)	123	140	42	67	28	400
12	Digital Media Planning and Buying	115	168	36	40	41	400
13	Web Analytics	86	176	38	62	38	400
	Total	1254	2295	455	625	571	5200
	Percentage	24%	44%	9%	12%	11%	100%

Responses to Prospect

Table 7: Responses to Prospect

Sr. No.	Area	Very strong	Strong	Neutral	Not much	Not at all	Total
1	Search Engine Optimization (SEO)	104	158	41	55	42	400
2	Search Engine Marketing (SEM)	107	157	33	63	40	400
3	Content Creation	104	153	39	44	60	400
4	Social Media Marketing (SMM)	109	186	45	32	28	400
5	Digital Display Advertising	90	156	37	66	51	400
6	Mobile Marketing	84	189	35	58	34	400
7	Interactive Marketing	111	138	35	70	46	400
8	Viral Marketing	105	123	41	72	59	400
9	Email Marketing	99	173	40	57	31	400
10	Affiliate Marketing	128	150	39	48	35	400
11	Online Public Relations (Online PR)	146	148	25	38	43	400
12	Digital Media Planning and Buying	71	223	23	27	56	400
13	Web Analytics	149	119	37	51	44	400
	Total	1407	2073	470	681	569	5200
	Percentage	27%	40%	9%	13%	11%	100%

Discussion

For positioning 28% of the respondents rated the 13 areas as Very well positioned, 35% as Well positioned, 7% Neutral, 16% Poorly positioned, and 14% Very poorly positioned. The well-positioned rating is significantly higher than the poor positioning. In case of performance 25% of the respondents rated the 13 areas as Excellent performance, 43% as Good performance, 8% as Neutral, 13% as Poor performance, and 10% Disgusting performance. The good performance rating is significantly higher than the poor performance. In case of problems 24% of the respondents rated the 13 areas as Very strong problem, 44% as Strong problem, 9% as Neutral, 12% as Not much of a problem, and 11% as Not a problem at all. The strong problem rating is significantly higher than mild problem. In case of prospects 27% of the respondents rated the 13 areas as Very strong prospect, 40% as Strong prospect, 9% as Neutral, 13% as Not much of a prospect, and 11% as Not a prospect at all. The strong prospect rating is significantly higher than the poor prospect.

Conclusion

Digital marketing and social media firms in India have grown at a rapid pace. From just 50 agencies in 2011, they have gone up to more than 700. This shows a very strong growth of digital marketing in India over the last decade. A range of areas in digital marketing like Search Engine Optimization (SEO), Search Engine Marketing (SEM), Content Creation, Social Media Marketing (SMM), Digital Display Advertising, Mobile Marketing, Interactive Marketing, Viral Marketing, Email Marketing, Affiliate Marketing, Online Public Relations (Online PR), Digital Media Planning and Buying and Web Analytics have advanced at a brisk pace. The positioning of the firms is quite strong. They also feel that there are significant prospects in all the 13 areas of digital marketing. However, the challenge is to overcome the problems to which the respondents have given a high rating.

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